

FATIGUE DAMAGE MODEL FOR SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS (PA6-GF30)

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SUMMARY

The present paper deals with the experimental identification and validation of a cumulative damage model developed for short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites [1]. The damage parameters are identified using longitudinal and transversal fatigue tests for glass fibre reinforced Polyamid-6 (PA6). The experimental validation of the developed modelling has been performed by comparison of damage predictions with experimental data from longitudinal and transversal tension-tension fatigue tests performed at different applied strain levels.

Keywords: Fatigue; Damage modelling; Short glass fibre; Experimental identification

INTRODUCTION

The present work is a contribution to the phenomenological modelling of fatigue non - linear cumulative diffuse damage in short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites. In such materials, fatigue damage kinetic exhibits three stages, namely: i) material softening and damage initiation, ii) coalescence and propagation of micro - cracks, iii) macroscopic cracks propagation and material failure [1-4]. The proposed model is built in the framework of the continuum damage mechanics (CDM) and aims at predicting these three stages of the damage evolution. This model, based on the approach initially proposed by Ladevèze and Le Dantec [5], extends previous approaches and takes into account the important stiffness reduction observed during the first stage. The above is modelled by the integration of a new evolution law expressing the damage rates as a function of the strain [6]. The model has been formulated in terms of strain energy, so that makes convenient its numerical implementation into the finite element code ABAQUS/Standard through a user defined material subroutine UMAT [7, 8].

An experimental identification is performed using longitudinal and transversal tension-tension fatigue tests giving rise to longitudinal and transversal damage denoted by d_{11} and d_{22} , respectively. Experimental damage evolutions as a function of number of cycles in both directions have been used into an inverse method aimed at determining the 8 damage parameters governing d_{11} and d_{22} evolutions for a glass fibre reinforced Polyamid-6 (PA6-GF30). Two different applied strain levels were used for the

identification procedure of the damage laws. The fatigue damage model is experimentally validated for longitudinal and transverse directions. Indeed, the comparison between the model damage predictions and the damage curves obtained from fatigue tests performed at different strain levels, not used for the identification, shows a good correlation for the studied composite material. Moreover, the modelling is able to capture the three stages of damage kinetic notably the first stage due to the material softening in short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics.

NEW FATIGUE DAMAGE MODEL

As indicated in the introduction, the damage evolution and accumulation in reinforced thermoplastic composites occur according to three stages. The developed model should be able to capture the three damage stages observed for these kinds of composite materials, notably the first stage where an important stiffness reduction occurs before reaching a steady damage accumulation prior the material failure. During the first few cycles, the damage kinetic is mainly due to the material softening depending on the applied strain or stress level.

In the proposed model the response of the undamaged material is assumed to be orthotropic linearly elastic and the damage is assumed to be diffuse. According to the continuum damage mechanics (CDM), the damage is introduced through three internal state variables, coupled to elastic behaviour. Indeed, the damage accumulation may bring about a stiffness reduction characterized by the decreasing of elastic moduli. These are expressed as follows: In-plane without transverse shear stress

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= E_{11}^0 (1 - d_{11}) \\ E_{22} &= E_{22}^0 (1 - d_{22}) \\ G_{12} &= G_{12}^0 (1 - d_{12}) \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

E_{11} : and E_{22} Longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli.

G_{12} : In plane shear moduli

d_{ij} : Internal damage state variables

The superscript 0 indicates the undamaged state of the material.

The elastic strain energy of a non damaged material is denoted hereafter (W_e) and is given by the following expression as a function of the strain tensor (ϵ_{ij}):

$$\begin{aligned} W_e &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \left[\left(E_{11}^0 \epsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} E_{11}^0 \epsilon_{22} \right) \epsilon_{11} + \left(\nu_{12} E_{22}^0 \epsilon_{11} + E_{22}^0 \epsilon_{22} \right) \epsilon_{22} \right] \\ &\quad + G_{12}^0 \gamma_{12}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

In the case a stiffness reduction, the strain energy of the damaged material, denoted by (W_d), is obtained from Eq. (1) where E_{11}^0 , E_{22}^0 and G_{12}^0 are substituted by the corresponding damaged moduli E_{11} , E_{22} and G_{12} .

Hence, one can express the strain energy of the damage material by:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_d = & \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \left[E_{11}^0 (1-d_{11}) \varepsilon_{11} \langle \varepsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_{22} \rangle_+ + E_{11}^0 \varepsilon_{11} \langle \varepsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_{22} \rangle_- \right] \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \left[E_{22}^0 (1-d_{22}) \varepsilon_{22} \langle \varepsilon_{22} + \nu_{12} \varepsilon_{11} \rangle_+ + E_{22}^0 \varepsilon_{22} \langle \varepsilon_{22} + \nu_{12} \varepsilon_{11} \rangle_- \right] \\
& + G_{12}^0 (1-d_{12}) \gamma_{12}^2
\end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

Where ($\langle A \rangle_+$) and ($\langle A \rangle_-$) stand for the positive and negative parts of amount A, respectively. Thus, the damage affects E_{11} (resp. E_{22}) only when $\varepsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_{22}$ (resp. $\varepsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_{22}$) is positive. Indeed, this makes sense and could be explained as following: when the material is subjected to a compressive loading, transverse matrix cracks are supposed to be closed up and do not have anymore influence on the damage evolution. During tension loading those cracks are active and contribute to the development of the damage.

The thermodynamic dual variables (Y_{ij}) associated to the damage variables d_{ij} are deduced from the strain energy (W_d) of the damaged material, as given by Eq. (4):

$$\begin{cases}
Y_{11} = -\frac{\partial W_d}{\partial d_{11}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} E_{11}^0 \varepsilon_{11} \langle \varepsilon_{11} + \nu_{21} \varepsilon_{22} \rangle_+ \\
Y_{22} = -\frac{\partial W_d}{\partial d_{22}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} E_{22}^0 \varepsilon_{22} \langle \varepsilon_{22} + \nu_{12} \varepsilon_{11} \rangle_+ \\
Y_{12} = -\frac{\partial W_d}{\partial d_{12}} = \frac{1}{2} G_{12}^0 \gamma_{12}^2
\end{cases} \tag{1.4}$$

Damage rates ($\partial d_{ij} / \partial N$) correspond to the damage kinetics and are expressed as a function of the thermodynamic forces (Y_{ij}). In the present work, damage rates are assumed to be the sum of two components: The first contribution is derived from the Norton-like power law. The second component is introduced in order to describe the stiffness reduction occurring during the first damage stage due to the material softening of reinforced thermoplastics. It is expressed by an exponential law of the dual forces. The developed model is then a complete model in the sense that the entire damage process (3 stages) could be described, notably the first stage. Damage rates are then given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial(d_{11})}{d(N)} &= \frac{\alpha_{11}\beta_{11}}{1+\beta_{11}}(Y_{11})^{\beta_{11}-1} + \lambda_{11}(Y_{11})\left(e^{-\delta_{11}N}\right) \\
\frac{\partial(d_{22})}{d(N)} &= \frac{\alpha_{22}\beta_{22}}{1+\beta_{22}}(Y_{22})^{\beta_{22}-1} + \lambda_{22}(Y_{22})\left(e^{-\delta_{22}N}\right) \\
\frac{\partial(d_{12})}{d(N)} &= \frac{\alpha_{12}\beta_{12}}{1+\beta_{12}}(Y_{12})^{\beta_{12}-1} + \lambda_{12}(Y_{12})\left(e^{-\delta_{12}N}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

Where α_{11} , β_{11} , λ_{11} and δ_{11} are the material damage parameters associated to the longitudinal direction. α_{12} , β_{12} , λ_{12} and δ_{12} are the material damage parameters related to shear damage and α_{22} , β_{22} , λ_{22} and δ_{22} are those characterising the damage in the transversal direction.

The instantaneous state variables $d_{ij}(N)$ are obtained by numerical integration of Eqs. (5), with initial conditions $d_{ij}(N=0)=d^{qs}_{ij}$. These initial values are function of the imposed displacement or load and are estimated just after the preloading stage during a fatigue test. In the case where the applied strain (or stress) is below a damage threshold value associated to the beginning of the damage process in the (i,j) direction, $d^{qs}_{ij}=0$.

EXPERIMENTAL IDENTIFICATION

Material

Material damage parameters identification cannot be achieved without experimental tests involving the three stages of damage. In the present paper, PA6-GF30 is studied; we focus on longitudinal and transversal tension-tension tests leading to a longitudinal and transversal damage (d_{11} and d_{22}). We consider fatigue tests performed in tension-tension. The studied composite material is a polyamide thermoplastic reinforced short glass fibre, denoted by PA6-GF30 hereafter. The reinforcement makes the material highly resistant to abrasion, compression, tension or bending.

Experimental procedure

The specimens used in the static and fatigue tensile tests were cut from thin plates. The geometry and dimensions of the tension specimens are shown in Figure 1. Fatigue tests were strain controlled and carried out using a servo-hydraulic machine. The imposed displacement wave was sinusoidal with constant amplitude. All tests were performed at room temperature. The mechanical properties of the material have been extracted from static tension tests. Some of the properties are given in Table 1.

Figure 1: Specimen used for tension tests (dimensions are in mm).

Table 1 : Monotonic mechanical properties of the studied material and standard deviations

Material	E^0 (MPa)	$\epsilon_{\text{damage Threshold}}(\%)$	$\epsilon_{\text{Rup}}(\%)$	$\sigma_{\text{UTS}}(\text{MPa})$
PA6-GF30 longitudinal direction	7042. (370)	0.7 (0.02)	5. (0.4)	114. (6)
PA6-GF30 transversal direction	3760. (689)	0.6 (0.01)	4.6 (0.6)	60.7 (3.2)

Experimental cyclic tests are driven by an applied displacement, see Figure 2. It is introduced the maximum strain ϵ_{max} and the minimum strain ϵ_{min} . It is usually defined the fatigue ratio by $R = \epsilon_{\text{min}} / \epsilon_{\text{max}}$. Note that ϵ_{rup} denotes the maximum strain reached when the material fails. Five strain levels ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 20\% \epsilon_{\text{rup}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 30\% \epsilon_{\text{rup}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 35\% \epsilon_{\text{rup}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 40\% \epsilon_{\text{rup}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 45\% \epsilon_{\text{rup}}$) have been conducted using three specimens for each different levels. The ratio R remains the same for the different configuration ($R = 0.3$). The frequency is 2 Hz. Some properties are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

Figure 2: Strain history obtained from an imposed displacement test. Note that the static pre-loading (up to the point F) could give rise to an initial damage representing the quasi-static damage (denoted by d_{qs} in the current work).

Table 2 Applied strain levels, initial modulus and the quasi static damage values determined through the static preloading for fatigue tests in longitudinal direction.

	Test 20%	Test 30%	Test 35%	Test 40%	Test 45%
$\epsilon_{\text{max}}(\%)$	1	1,5	1,75	2	2,25
$E^0_{11}(\text{MPa})$	7435	7140	7310	6900	7400
d^{qs}_{11}	0.05	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.12

a. Longitudinal direction

b. Transversal direction

Figure 3: Experimental results of the evolution of the damage d_{11} and d_{22} versus the number of cycles N . The studied composite material was subjected to tension-tension displacement controlled fatigue test. Five maximum applied strains ϵ_{max} were considered: 20%, 30%, 35%, 40% and 45% of the total fracture strain ϵ_{rup} measured during a static tensile test. The fatigue ratio was $R=0.3$.

Table 3 Applied strain levels, initial modulus and the quasi static damage values determined through the static preloading for fatigue tests in transversal direction.

	Test 20%	Test 30%	Test 35%	Test 40%	Test 45%
ϵ_{max} (%)	1	1,5	1,75	2	2,25
E_{22}^0 (MPa)	4108	4160	3980	4320	3890
d_{22}^{qs}	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.12

It is shown on Figure 3 the evolution of d_{11} and d_{22} versus N obtained from experimental fatigue tension-tension tests at different ϵ_{\max} ($\epsilon_{\max}=20\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=30\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=35\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=40\% \epsilon_{rup}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}=45\% \epsilon_{rup}$). It is observed that even if data are quite scattered, an increase in ϵ_{\max} leads to an increase in the damage rate, and an enhanced d_{11}^{qs} and d_{22}^{qs} . This is due to a more cumulative damage occurring when the maximum strain passes from $20\% \epsilon_{rup}$ to $30\% \epsilon_{rup}$ to $35\% \epsilon_{rup}$ to $40\% \epsilon_{rup}$ to $45\% \epsilon_{rup}$. In Figure 2, the point F defines the end of the quasi-static step. It is the highest for $\epsilon_{\max}=45\% \epsilon_{rup}$ and the lowest for $\epsilon_{\max}=20\% \epsilon_{rup}$. In the latter case, less damage is cumulated up to the point F. As a result, the quasi-static damage amount is reduced.

Damage parameter identification

The goal is to identify the parameters involved in the damage evolution, in the longitudinal direction (α_{11} , β_{11} , λ_{11} and δ_{11}) and in the transverse direction (α_{22} , β_{22} , λ_{22} and δ_{22}) for the PA6-GF30. The identification procedure is detailed for the longitudinal direction. The same strategy has been adopted to identify the transverse behaviour. For convenience, in the description of the procedure, the subscript 11 is omitted. An objective function representing, in the least squares sense, the difference between experimental and numerical data [9-10] has been built and minimised. The cost function is written as:

$$S(\underline{P}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^a [d_i^{exp} - d_i^N(\underline{P})]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^a (d_i^{exp})^2} \quad (1.6)$$

d_i could d_i^{11} for longitudinal direction and d_i^{22} for transverse direction

where a is the number of experimental data. d_i^{exp} measures the damage in the longitudinal direction or transverse direction and d_i^N is the computed value obtained from the modelling (Eq 1.5) with $d_{11}=d$. \underline{P} is the parameter vector that contains (α , β , λ , δ).

The minimisation of the cost function is an iterative procedure. At each step, the vector \underline{P} is re-estimated (\underline{P} becomes $\underline{P} + \Delta \underline{P}$) and the cost function S is re-evaluated. $\Delta \underline{P}$ is computed by using a Levenberg-Marquardt. The iterative procedure is stopped when two consecutive values of the cost function satisfy: $\|S(\underline{P} + \Delta \underline{P}) - S(\underline{P})\| < 10^{-5}$. Namely, the cost function becomes stationary. The parameters α , β , λ and δ are identified by using experimental data obtained from tests corresponding to $\epsilon_{\max} = 30\% \epsilon_{rup}$ and $\epsilon_{\max} = 40\% \epsilon_{rup}$. The comparison between experimental data used for the identification strategy and the computed damages are presented on Figure 4. Moreover, it has been assessed that the identification procedure does not depend on the initial values of α , β , λ and δ .

a. Longitudinal direction

b. Transversal direction

Figure 4: Comparison between experimental and calculated damage data for five configurations ($\epsilon_{\max}=30\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=30\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=35\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=40\% \epsilon_{rup}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}=45\% \epsilon_{rup}$).

Finally, the set of parameters determined by the inverse procedure is validated on the experimental curves obtained in the case where $\epsilon_{\max}=20\% \epsilon_{rup}$, $\epsilon_{\max}=35\% \epsilon_{rup}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}=45\% \epsilon_{rup}$. Figure 4 shows the comparison between experimental data and numerical calculations for the parameters computed from the identification procedure.

CONCLUSION

In this work, a new cumulative fatigue damage model in short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics is developed and experimentally validated for a glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic: PA6-GF. These composites are characterized by an evolution of the damage in three stages. The proposed model is able to capture the three stages, especially the first one specific to composite materials with thermoplastic matrix.

This paper presents a first identification strategy based on homogeneous tensile fatigue tests performed in the longitudinal and transversal directions of a PA6-GF composite. Strain controlled fatigue tests at different levels have been carried-out to identify the 8 parameters governing the evolution of the longitudinal and transversal damage variables (d_{11}) and (d_{22}). These parameters are identified on the basis of experimental data obtained from fatigue tests conducted at two different applied strain levels: $\epsilon_{\max}=30\%\epsilon_{\text{rup}}$ and $\epsilon_{\max}=40\%\epsilon_{\text{rup}}$. The developed model is experimentally validated for both material directions. Indeed, the comparison between the model damage predictions and the damage curves obtained from fatigue tests performed at: $\epsilon_{\max}=20\%$, $\epsilon_{\max}=35\%$ and $\epsilon_{\max}=45\%$ of ϵ_{rup} shows a good correlation in both material directions.

A second identification strategy is currently ongoing. It is based on the use of optical whole-field displacement/strain measurements by digital images correlation coupled to an inverse method from one single coupon. It is worth noting that the mechanical test must give rise to heterogeneous stress/strain fields. Indeed, in this case, the constitutive parameters are expected to be all involved in the response of the specimen.

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